

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

Volume I Issue VI

ECHOES *of* EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

OCTOBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

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ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

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[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17445558](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17445558)

Becoming Me: A Journey to Success

"Life tested me not to break me, but to reveal the strength I never knew I had"

There was a time when nothing felt certain. Dreams seemed out of reach. Each day became a silent battle between hope and doubt. I was just a simple girl with many dreams. I was raised poor, with no home of our own or rich parents. I was just passing the day. I learned the meaning of life and suffering from an early age. I watched my parents work hard all the time and make countless sacrifices to put food on the table, even when money was tight. Those moments planted in me a desire to change our life story. Their silent strength taught and inspires me that success is never given but earned through patience, hard work, and faith.

I began my own hustle at a young age, not because I wanted to, but because I had no other choice. I fabricated brooms with my little hands, vended puto and banana cue under the scorching sun, and took with me the silent hope of being able to somehow help my family. As I recall looking up at the friends of my childhood, and watching them laugh, share snacks, free from care in ways that I couldn't even dream of being.

I was jealous of their pretty dresses at school parties and programs, their new bags and gadgets that seemed to replicate a life free from tension. Through my jolly and humorous side, I hid the pain, envy, and hardships that life had given me. I faced moments that nearly made me give up, the times when the weight of responsibilities, failures, and disappointments felt unbearable.

Never thought I would be able to pursue college. When my parents separated due to conflicts and misunderstandings and all other reasons that my siblings and I couldn't understand, I felt so hopeless, drained, and so emotional that I couldn't bear the situation. As the saying goes, "when it rains, it pours," literally happened to my life. Despite the numerous problems and struggles, I have remained resilient and brave in life, as I always put my faith in God and believe that everything happens for a reason.

I never stopped praying, asking God to bless me, help me change my life, bear all the hardships and trials, and make me strong and brave enough to overcome them. As a proud member of the Iglesia Ni Cristo, my faith was strong, and I knew God never left me. He made me realize that pain was never meant to punish, but to prepare me.

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Grateful for the family God sent to be an instrument in allowing me to finish college, even in a short period of time. They accepted me as their own, providing for my needs. I endured the longing for my own family while being away from them. I had to be strong and brave to fulfill my dream. I gathered all my strength and courage to complete my studies so I could repay my parents' sacrifices. Every day was filled with longing, missing my family, and wondering why life had to be this way. I wanted to be with them, yet I managed to overcome those moments so I could continue my journey toward becoming the person I aspire to be.

As a member of the Church of Christ, I hold steadfast faith that remaining firm and steadfast in my election and duty will lead me toward the success I have long prayed for – a life that would make all those struggles worthwhile. God never abandoned me; He led and guided my way. Finally, I finished my college journey and passed the board exam. I know deep within my heart it was God who made everything possible.

A year after my graduation, I took the risk to apply to my Alma Mater as an instructor. Despite the fear of rejection, I chose to trust in God's plan. And yes, He did not fail me. I was hired and became a regular faculty member at the age of 21. I was never good at anything, yet God strengthened me and blessed me with the wisdom and knowledge I needed for the job He gave me. I worked so hard to enhance my skills and improve myself so I could be an effective educator. As a novice teacher, I had encountered failures and endured struggles, but never did I think of giving up. I faced heartaches once more, though they were no longer strangers to me. Instead, they became reminders of how far I had come. Through every challenge, I keep on telling myself, "This too shall pass".

Now, I am living the dream I once whispered in prayer. Life feels lighter now- my family and my career. I know there is still much to learn; as the saying goes, "Malayo pa pero malayo na", still, I am grateful and happy for how far I have come and for every milestone I have reached. God made it all possible. Truly, you will realize that everything you have gone through was a blessing in disguise.

"The trials of today will not last forever. God is turning your pain into purpose and your struggles into testimonies." – Romans 8:18.